

Remotely Sensed Ecosystem benefits of tree cover on Enugu Campus of the University of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the principal greenhouse gas responsible for the global warming phenomenon. Apart from the various ecosystem benefits (eco-benefits) that trees offer, such as maintaining healthy soil, safeguarding water supplies, reducing global warming, and creating habitats for wildlife, trees can also release oxygen into the atmosphere through photosynthesis – a process by which green plants utilize carbon dioxide (CO₂) to manufacture their biomass in the presence of sunlight. Nevertheless, despite Nigeria's unwavering dedication to promoting the Nature Positive University Approach, little is known about the precise distribution of tree cover and the environmental advantages of trees storing carbon emissions on Nigerian university campuses. Therefore, the goal of this paper is to support a nature-positive university approach for a sustainable learning environment by evaluating the carbon emissions and eco-benefits of tree cover distribution on the University of Nigeria's Enugu campus (UNEC) in Southeast Nigeria using data from two open-source remote sensing tools: Global Forest Watch and i-Tree Canopy Cover Assessment. According to the results, UNEC's tree cover increased by 0.41%, that is less than 1.0 hectare, between 2000 and 2020. This percentage gain implies that trees were added to the University's landmass during the study period. Carbon credits totaling ₦37,861,404±1,642,223 are produced as eco-benefits of 339 sampled trees in the study area. Furthermore, this study shows that the trees sampled store 129.34±5.61 tons of carbon annually and sequester 474.25±20.57 tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalent into their biomass. There was 85% classification agreement between the training data obtained from Google Earth App and the categorized landcover classes in i-Tree Software. In conclusion, all Nigerian university campuses must continuously increase and preserve the amount of tree cover on their grounds in order for the nation to satisfactorily obtain the UN's Nature Positive Status. It is hereby suggested that the next research line evaluate a ground-based survey to validate the data regarding the actual tree species and diameter at breast height in order to quantify the actual tree volume available within UNEC.

KEYWORDS: Carbon Emissions, Eco-benefits, Global Forest Watcher, Native Positivity Approach, Open-Source Remote Sensing Tool, Tree Canopy Cover, UNEC

INTRODUCTION

Trees use a process called photosynthesis to absorb carbon dioxide (CO₂) and convert it to oxygen (Matey, 2024). In addition to enhancing the quality and quantity of the air where they are planted, trees also preserve healthy soil, safeguard water supplies, reduce global warming, and benefit wildlife (Han *et al.*, 2024). Any tall plant with branches and leaves emerging from a long, woody stem known as a trunk is considered a tree, according to FAO (2014). FAO (2014) adds that the length of a forest tree's trunk is what distinguishes it.

Every tree generally improves people's social and economic conditions as well as the environment: rural or urban (Chambers-Ostler *et al.*, 2024). However, The Forest Resource Assessment 2000 by the Food and Agriculture (FAO) of the United Nations in 2000 and since modified in FAO, (2020) defines a 'forest' as: 'land with a tree canopy cover of more than 10 percent and area of more than 0.5 ha. Although there are billions of trees on Earth, not all of them are included in the FAO's definition of "forest" and "other wooded land." Consequently, such a situation leads to the adoption of the terminology, "Trees outside the forest (TOF)". TOF is refers to as the trees

found in non-forest areas such as farms, cities, highways, university campuses, etc. (FAO, 2000).

Since the contributions of every tree on planet earth is relevant, there is the dire need for everyone to promote “A nature positive approach”. According to the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2021), “Nature positive approach means enhancing the resilience of our planet and societies to halt and reverse nature loss.” This World Economic Forum report classified the “Nature positive approach” is regarded as a Climate Action, because, Nature positivity concept demands that, nature – species and ecosystems – are constantly being repaired and regenerating rather than being in decline. Therefore, achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and keeping global warming to 1.5 degrees requires the protection of natural environment (Schmidt *et al.*, 2024).

Accordingly, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the University of Oxford, in collaboration with the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, launched the "Nature Positivity Universities Alliance" in December 2022 during the 15th Conference OF Parties (COP-15) on Biodiversity (Nature

Positive Universities, 2022). The mission of a Nature Positivity University is to collaborate with other networks in order to promote nature

on campuses, in supply chains, and in urban areas.

Figure 1: Global goal for nature positivity by 2030; adapted from (Nature Positive Universities, 2022)

Figure 1 emphasizes the goal of a Nature Positivity University to contribute to halting and reversing the destruction of nature by 2030 and continue to embark on nature recovery until 2050 (WEF, 2021). That is, everything a university does, from its teaching and research work to the operations and supply chains that keep it running. The foregoing analogies necessitate the need for behind this study on ‘Using open-source remote sensing tool to quantify carbon emissions in correlation with tree cover availability on the Enugu campus of University of Nigeria’.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Nature Positive Universities need to take global action to support the post-2020 global biodiversity framework's implementation

(IUCN, 2022). Many college campuses are trying to increase their green spaces and tree canopy in an effort to improve the quality of life for their residents (Griffith University, (2015). In order to meet the targets of the Paris Climate Agreement, countries must report their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and explain how they plan to cut back on greenhouse gas emissions. This includes using nature-based offsets to preserve trees and providing funding to rural and indigenous communities that depend on forests and other essential resources (United Nations, 2024).

However, despite Nigeria's commitment to promoting the Nature Positive University Approach, little to no information is available about the precise amount of tree cover

distribution with their eco-benefits on carbon emissions sequestered by trees within Nigerian university campuses. In accordance with the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of the 2015 Paris Climate Change Agreement, such a scenario results in a research gap regarding the total amount of carbon emissions that universities have contributed to reducing within their campuses (United Nations, 2024). To bridge the foregoing research gap, this research attempts to answer the question: Is tree cover related to carbon emissions using open-source Global Forest Watch? Therefore, the aim of paper is to investigate the

relationship between carbon emissions fluxes and university campus tree canopy distribution at the University of Nigeria, which is located in Enugu, Nigeria, in an effort.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

This study was conducted at the Enugu Campus of the University of Nigeria (lat. 6.42320° and lon. 7.50453°), Southeast Nigeria. The study area ((**Figure 2**) is predominantly a land area spanning 129.37 hectares (ha) in a lowland area in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Figure 2: NDVI generated map produced from Sentinel-2 image of November 15, 2023 over UNEC on lat. 6.4247°; lon. N 7.5031° E and lat. 6.42360; lon. 7.50362

Generally in Enugu State, the dry season runs from November to March of every year. High temperatures of up to 38°C (100°F) are experienced in the afternoons of dry seasons

lower temperatures are experienced during the rainy season, which spans from April to October (NBS, 2017). Nonetheless, the study area records

2,000 to 3,000 mm of rainfall every year (NBS, 2017).

Analysis of deforestation and tree cover rates with Global Forest Watch Tool

The carbon emission rates and tree cover loss and tree cover gain were computed in this study. First, the Global Forest Watcher (GFW) was used to characterize the trees' gain-and-loss status in terms of tree cover. The Global Forest Watch (GFW) Tool shows the annual change in tree cover in the chosen area, which is defined as the replacement of vegetation at stand level that is higher than five meters. Methodological steps were adapted from Ogbodo et al., (2024) and Ogbodo et al., (2023). The percentage tree cover gains and losses in the Year 2000 – 2020 were extracted from the Global Forest Watcher.

i-Tree Canopy Cover Assessment and Tree Benefits

The i-Tree Canopy Cover Assessment model was used in this study because it gives urban foresters the thorough information they need to make decisions about urban forests that are sustainable. The model can be used to estimate the urban forest structure, including species composition, number of trees, tree density, and other factors (i-Tree Eco User's Manual, 2021). Originally, the Tool is developed for tree-level data collection in the United States of America. Therefore, urban forest projects outside of the United States require the collection of additional data, such as location data (such as country, continent, latitude, longitude, elevation, mean minimum temperatures, ozone state, etc.) and precipitation information. The tool utilized a random sampling method. The spatial distribution of sampling plots at the study area

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of sampling plots in the study area

Monetary and statistical computations

With respect to Table 2, all the currency amounts obtained were rounded to the nearest Naira (₦). Base on sample errors of sampled and classified points are the standard errors of removal and benefits amounts. The 3.060 tons (t) of carbon, or ₦79, 834.20 per ton of CO₂, that represent the amount of carbon emissions sequestered was rounded up. The amount of carbon stored in trees was valued based on 76.848 tons of carbon, or 281,776 tons of CO₂, per hectare, and is rounded. The currency value in Naira (₦), rounded up, is based on ₦79, 834.20/t of CO₂ or ₦292, 725.40/t of carbon.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tree cover density and carbon emissions in UNEC, Enugu

This research examined the 129.40 hectares (ha) of the University of Nigeria's Enugu Campus, popularly known as UNEC (Figure 2), in order to determine the increases and decreases in tree cover and to determine the exact amount of carbon emissions that can be produced on the campus.

In 2020, UNEC, Enugu had 72 ha of land above 10% tree cover, extending over 55.6% of its land area. The tree heights in UNEC fall within between 3m and 7 meters tall on the GEDI data. The tree cover and deforestation

analysis using the GFW Tool indicates that, between 2000 and 2020, the UNEC Campus gained almost one (1) hectare of tree cover amounting to 0.41% of its entire area. The 30-m spatial resolution global forest canopy height map produced from the 2020 Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) lidar forest in the GFW Tool shows that the trees on the UNEC campus range in height from 3 to 7 metres. However, there was no loss of tree cover due to logging nor bushfires because, there were no sign of deforestation during the period, 2000 - 2020. Between 2001 and 2022, the trees at UNEC Campus sequester -4.94 ktCO₂eq/year from the atmosphere; amounting to a -4.94 ktCO₂eq/year net carbon sink. A year later, i.e. between 2001 and 2023, forests in UNEC, emitted a net carbon sink of -4.73 tCO₂e/year.

However, there were no deforestation related emissions on campus throughout the understudy period. This result scientifically makes sense because the UNEC Campus is not a forest, where deforestation related activities are expected.

Results of the Tree canopy assessments using i-Tree remote sensing tool

The Tree and other landcover signatures analyzed in the i-Tree Canopy Assessment Tool (Table 1) were validated in Google Earth (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Training data obtained from Google Earth Remote Sensing Tool <https://earth.google.com/web/>

A total of 1,106 landcover classes were sampled in research. A breakdown of the number sampled per landcover class is provided in Figure 5. The proportion of landcover and the area covered at each sampled site are shown in Table 5.

Table 1: Natural signatures of the sampled landcover classes in the study area

Landcover class	Symbol	No. of sample points	% landcover \pm SE	Area (ha) \pm SE
Tree/Shrub	T	359	32.46 \pm 1.41	42.27 \pm 1.83
Herbaceous Grass	H	330	29.84 \pm 1.38	38.85 \pm 1.79
Buildings - Impervious	B	119	10.76 \pm 0.93	14.01 \pm 1.21
Road - Impervious	R	49	4.43 \pm 0.62	5.77 \pm 0.81
Bare-land	B	214	19.35 \pm 1.19	25.20 \pm 1.55
Concreted Surfaces - Impervious	C	35	3.16 \pm 0.53	4.12 \pm 0.69
Total		1106	100	130.22

Based on Table 5, it can be inferred that the percentage of tree canopy is 32.46 \pm 1.41, which spans across an area ranging from 42.27 \pm 1.83 hectares. Recall that, the UNEC has a total of 129.40 hectares (ha). Comparably, the

percentage coverage for the remaining sampled classes is as follows: grasses (29.84 \pm 1.38) on a land area of 38.85 \pm 1.79 ha, Bare-land (19.35 \pm 1.19) with an area of 25.20 \pm 1.55 ha and Impervious Building

Surface (10.76±0.93) on a 14.01±1.21 ha of UNEC land.

Table 2: Tree Carbon storage Benefits in the study area

Description	Carbon in tons (t) ±SE	CO ₂ eq. in tons (t)±SE	Amount in Naira (₦) ±SE
Annual rate of carbon emissions sequester in Trees	129.34±5.61	474.25±20.57	₦37,861,404±1,642,223
Non-annual overall estimates of carbon storage in trees	3,248.24±5.61	11,910.21±516.60	₦950,841,926±41,242,391

Table 2 displays the results of the carbon storage valuation that was determined in this study using the i-Tree Canopy Tool. The UNEC is predicated to sequester 474.25±20.57 tons of CO₂eq annually, which should yield a carbon credit valued at

₦37,861,404±1,642,223. Equally, ₦950,841,926±41,242,391 must be acquired in carbon credits in order to preserve 3,248.24±5.61 tons in 359 tree-level carbon storage.

Table 3: Air pollution removal Benefits of Trees in the study area

Abbr.	Description	Amount (kg)±SE	Monetary value (₦) ±SE	Ranking based on ₦ values
CO	Carbon Monoxide removed annually	42.79±1.86	28,716±1,246	6th
NO ₂	Nitrogen Dioxide removed annually	214.05±9.28	9,014±391	4th
O ₃	Ozone removed annually	2,275.80±98.71	453,000±19,649	3rd
SO ₂	Sulfur Dioxide removed annually	213.78±9.27	1,556±68	5th
PM2.5	Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns removed annually	112.47±4.88	948,082±41,123	2nd
PM10	Particulate Matter greater than 2.5 microns and less than 10 microns removed annually	808.70±35.08	2,719,305±117,949	1st
Total		3,667.59±159.08 kg	₦4,159,674±180,425	

Note: Air pollution estimates are in kg/ha/year: CO = 1.012 at ₦671.12; NO₂ = 5.064 at ₦42.11; O₃ = 53.842 at ₦199.05; SO₂ = 5.058 at ₦7.28; PM2.5 = 2.661 at ₦8,429.81; PM10 = 19.133 at ₦3,362.55

One of the primary eco-benefits of trees that is investigated in this study relates to air pollution using the i-Tree Canopy Software. The results of the analysis are shown in Table 3. The 129.34±5.61 tons of carbon storage in the study area have the

capacity to reduce greenhouse gas emissions on an annual basis. Particulate matter greater than 2.5 microns but less than 10 microns (PM10) has the greatest yearly monetary value at 808.70±35.08 kg, with a monetary of

₦2,719,305±117,949. The following groups of greenhouse gases are removed from the atmosphere by the trees in study area on an annual basis: Ozone (2,275.80±98.71 kg amounting to ₦453,000±19,649); Particulate Matter less than 2.5 microns (112.47±4.88 kg,

worth: ₦948,082±41,123); Nitrogen Dioxide (214.05±9.28 kg, ₦9,014±391) and Carbon Monoxide (42.79±1.86 kg, ₦ 28.716±1,246). From Table 5.5.3, these air pollution gases are ranked second, third, fourth, and fifth, in that order.

Table 4: Hydrological benefits of Trees in the study area

Eco Benefit	Amount (kl)±SE	Value ±SE	
		\$	₦
Avoided Runoff	354.99±15.40	\$37±0	56517.50±0
Evaporation	29,290.30±1,270.46	NA	NA
Interception	29,436.48±1,276.80	NA	NA
Transpiration	45,387.72±1,968.67	NA	NA
Potential Evaporation	222,705.04±9,659.74	NA	NA
Potential Evapotranspiration	222,705.04±9,659.74	NA	NA

Note: Hydrological estimates are in kl/ha/year at ₦/kl/year as follows: Avoided runoff = 8.399 at ₦3,675.64; Evaporation = 692.961 at Not applicable (NA); Interception = 696.419 at NA; Transpiration = 1,073.800 at NA; Potential Evaporation = 5,268.842 at NA; Potential Evapotranspiration = 5,268.842 at NA

From Table 4, the monetary value of trees in the study area in curbing runoff of 354.99±15.40 kl is 1, ₦304,833±56,597. Likewise, the hydrological value of forest trees was also evaluated in this study using the i-Tree Canopy Software. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 4. In this study, trees provide the following hydrological benefits: (i) Potential Evaporation (222,705.04±9,659.74 kl); (ii) Potential Evapotranspiration (222,705.04±9,659.74kl), (iii) Transpiration (45,387.72±1,968.67 kl), (iv) Interception (29,436.48±1,276.80 kl) and (v) Evaporation (29,290.30±1,270.46 kl).

DISCUSSION

The tree canopy cover in any given location can be determined using the i-Tree Canopy Tool. This Tool is a web-based application that can be used anywhere in the world and is fast, easy to use, and free of cost. In this Thesis, the i-Tree Canopy Tool was used to statistically estimate tree benefits based on the monetary values (in Naira) of tree-level carbon storage, air pollution removal and hydrological benefits of trees at UNEC, Nigeria. There is spatial heterogeneity in carbon storage and sequestration of forest trees in the study area. The i-Tree Canopy Assessment Tool provided the default values (the multipliers) of air pollutant removal rates ($\text{gm}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$) and

monetary values ($\$ \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) for a unit tree cover (Nowak, 2021). The study demonstrates that increasing the size of the sample points can lead to improvements in the precision and accuracy of land cover classification and other eco-benefits computation when utilizing the Photo Interpretation (PI) Method (Figure 4) of the i-Tree Canopy Assessment software. There have been variations in the scope and methodologies used in earlier research on the application of the i-Tree canopy Assessment Tool in Nigeria. Therefore, it is impossible to draw any significant comparisons between the conclusions of this study and those of the previous publications on use of i-Tree Canopy Assessment Tool by Olusola and Aladesanmi, (2022) and Pelemo *et al.*, (2020). For example, Pelemo *et al.*, (2020) assessed forest canopy cover and tree benefits in Okomu National Park of Edo State, South-south Nigeria. Two key differences between UNEC and Okomu National Park are that the former is made up of a much smaller patch of urban indices, while the latter is subject to stricter forest conservation regulations. Although Olusola and Aladesanmi's study from 2022 assessed the ecosystem services provided by trees in an urban setting in Ekiti State, Southwest, Nigeria, the study location for this study is a university campus situated within the Southeastern region of Nigeria.

When comparing the use of the i-Tree Canopy Assessment Tool with ground-based estimates for carbon storage and eco-benefits analysis, Adekunle *et al.*, (2012) found that the monthly monetary values of forest tree environmental service functions total ₦21,743. The method of this study, as shown in Table 1 and Table 2, differ from those of Adekunle *et al.* (2012) in that the latter used questionnaire-based approaches, whilst the former sampled and assessed trees, remotely.

LIMITATION OF THE I-TREE CANOPY TOOL

The ability of the user to accurately classify each point into its appropriate class determines how accurate the analysis is. The precision and standard error of the estimates both rise with the number of points and decrease with it, respectively. The standard error will be too high if there aren't enough classified points, making it impossible to truly be certain of the outcome.

CONCLUSION

This study has proven the capability of open-source remote sensing platform such as the Global Forest Watch of the World Resources Institute (WRI) in quantifying the emissions rates from tropical deforestation scenarios in

the University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus. Therefore, this study has developed new frontier methods for tree-level carbon storage and eco-benefits in the University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, using freely available remote sensing data and tools. It offered details on the rates of carbon emissions brought on by tree cover availability in the study area.

In conclusion therefore, all Nigerian university campuses must continuously increase and preserve the amount of tree cover on their grounds in order for the nation to satisfactorily obtain the UN's Nature Positive Status. It is hereby suggested that the next research line evaluate a ground-based survey to validate the data regarding the actual tree species and diameter at breast height in order to quantify the actual tree volume available within UNEC.

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- Journal: Ajibade, B., S.A.E. Bolarinwa, E.B. Ajanusi, M. Bamidele, T. Bonire, J.A. Bolorunduro, P.M. Papka, C. Mariojouis (2011). Local people's understanding and perceptions of climate change: The case of Lagos, Nigeria. *Nigerian Climate Change Research* 21: 93-105.
- Book: Ibrahim, I.J. and R. Haruna (2009). *Trends in Contraceptives' Utilization in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Chapter in a Book: Gren, I.M. (2008). Cost-effective population control measures. In: *Managing Population Explosion*. Eds. I.M. Gren, K. Turner, and F. Joseph, pp143-152. London: Earthscan.
- Thesis/ Dissertation: Garba, A.J. (2005). Impacts of Organic Amendments on Fertility of an Alfisol in Ibadan, Nigeria. PhD Thesis, Geography Department, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Internet: Wikipedia (2006). Causes and consequences of desertification. <http://www.wikipedia.com/articles/139/desertification>. (Accessed March 15, 2012).

Notes

Short notes, footnotes and technical comments should be incorporated as notes.

Figures, Photographs, and Tables

Figures (graphs, line drawings, maps) should as much as possible be produced using computer-aided methods. Copies of Figures should be submitted on separate pages and numbered consecutively. Figure texts should be fully explanatory. Photos and Figures should be of high quality (a minimum resolution of 600 dpi in the format TIFF, EPS, GIF, JPEG or PPT), and be labelled with the photographer's and author's name. Figures should be prepared in a form that allows for reduction in size. Tables should be no more than ½ A4 page. Authors must ensure explaining all abbreviations used. Whenever possible the information in Tables should instead be presented in a figure.

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After typesetting of accepted papers, authors shall be sent proof copies for vetting. The purpose of the proof is to check for typesetting or conversion errors and the completeness and accuracy of the text, tables and figures. Substantial changes in content—e.g., new results, corrected values, title and authorship—are not allowed without the approval of the Editor

On publication, a PDF file (e-offprint) containing the published article and a hard copy of the published journal in which the article appeared will be sent to the corresponding author.

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